

Short introduction of SUSTAINCELL project

SUSTAINCELL

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Project information:

Project title	Durable and Sustainable component supply chain for high performance fuel cells and electrolyzers HORIZON-JTI-CLEANH2-2022-1
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Coordinator	Marie-Laure Fontaine, SINTEF
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1 Partners

SUSTAINCELL gathers 10 partners from 7 European countries with complementary expertise and outstanding infrastructure ensuring successful completion of the project's ambitious goals. Each partner has a specific role, complementary to others and essential for SUSTAINCELL outcomes, as summarized here and shown in figure 1:

- SINTEF is a research centre acting as coordinator and is involved with 3 groups of the Sustainable Technology Department: a) Thin Film and Membrane Technologies group has world leading expertise in PCCELS technologies, notably being coordinator of 2 EU projects; b) Battery and H₂ technology group has a long track record of EU projects and experience in low-temperature PEM/AEM ELs and FCs; c) Industrial Economy group has extensive expertise in Sustainability and process optimization and will contribute to the LCA study.
- CNRS and its affiliated entity, University of Montpellier (UM), main expertise is in the development, characterisation and validation of materials for low temperature fuel cells and electrolyzers, with contributions to the field of fluorine-free proton conducting membrane development, PGM-free catalysts for PEMFC and AEMFC, and nanomaterials developments for PEM and AEM fuel cells and electrolyzers.
- CEA is a research centre with focus on SOEC/SOFC with large activities in national and European projects, spanning from manufacturing to EoL processes routes. CEA is also actively involved in the development of low temperature PEM. CEA will also perform LCA and LCIA activities and will focus on EoL SOEL recycling.
- FZJ-HI ERN has long experience in the development of PEMFC and PEMEL, specializing in F-free and F-lean polymer and their recycling, and more recently, with increasing activity in AEMEL and AEMFC.
- DTU has been at the forefront of R&I on electrolytic hydrogen production, including the development of more efficient and reliable materials, cell components/architectures and

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processing routes for SOEL, PCCELs, AEL, AEMEL, AEMFC.

- TECNALIA is a leading Research and Technological Development Centre in Europe covering the whole value chain of hydrogen and will use its expertise for the development of PEMEL/PEMFC electrocatalysts and MEAs, as well as for the development of PGM and non-noble metals recovery.
- VTT is a non-profit R&D organization active which will provide its large expertise and infrastructure for reliable testing of single cells of both low and high temperature technologies.
- DLR is a German national research institute with long-term experience in fuel cells (SOFC, PEMFC, DMFC and AFC) and water electrolysis (alkaline, PEM, AEM, SOEC), production technologies e.g., plasma technology, and system technology. In the project, DLR will focus on the development of new catalysts for PEMFC, MEAs for PEMEL and AEMEL and new electrodes and cells designs for SOEL and PCCEL.

The consortium also gathers two partners from Switzerland.

- EPFL is active since 30 years in SOC materials, cells and stacks characterisation and modelling, specialised in (a) 3D electrode microstructure acquisition and quantification (segmentation algorithms) to develop new metrics (accessible TPB, curvature, dihedral angle based on interfacial Ni/ceramic energy), and in (b) electrochemical process understanding via EIS, DRT and THD. EPFL also has a strong activity on non-CRM electrode and membrane development for alkaline water electrolysis.
- HESSO, represented by the School of Engineering, through the Institute of Sustainable Energy has an extensive expertise in LCA and sustainability metrics to evaluate energy transformation and storage technologies. HESSO has developed several characterization models to assess emissions and resources consumption & dissipation within LCA. HESSO has been involved in several EU projects supporting design and development of more sustainable fuel cells technologies in collaboration with EPFL. HESSO will lead WP5 on sustainability and criticality of materials through its Sustainable Development Center, created in conjunction with EPFL and associated to the CIRAI Center in Montreal.

The partners gather an outstanding infrastructure to complete the tasks of SUSTAINCELL. To ensure reliability of results, the project will use (and if non existing) defined harmonized protocols for comparison of results between partners (samples preparation, parameters for characterization, e.g. voltage of SEM, and testing).

Figure 1. Partners' activities in the project.

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2 Objectives

The SUSTAINCELL project aims at supporting the European industry in the development of the next generation electrolyser and fuel cell technologies (both low and high temperature) by developing a sustainable European supply chain of materials, components and cells, significantly less reliant on critical raw materials (CRM), with lower environmental footprint and costs, and higher performance and durability than existing technologies. This will rely on scientific breakthrough innovations with the development of eco-design guidelines and environmentally friendly manufacturing routes applied for the production of new CRM-lean and/or CRM-free materials and architectures designed for maximising functionalities and durability, while decreasing CRM content per unit cell. The new flexible and scalable processing routes will exhibit higher productivity, as well as reduced utilities consumption and greenhouse gas emissions.

The following **specific objectives** of SUSTAINCELL are listed below with quantifiable targets reported in table 1.

O1: Harvesting and expanding European knowledge and know-how on CRM identification, substitution, recovery and recycling strategies and value chains

This will be achieved by gathering existing expertise and public data from European and international research and industrial communities to map out existing and future strategies for handling CRM in the whole value chain. The project will promote active communication and engagement of industrial and knowledge-based stakeholders to contribute to the *delivery of technology roadmaps for integrating SUSTAINCELL solutions in FC and EL technology deployment scenarios*. Stakeholders include past and running projects, members from industry, academic and industrial networks (ERMA, JRC, Mission Innovation 2.0, EMIRI, EERA, SPIRE, etc).

O2: Ensuring replacement and/or reduction of critical raw materials per unit cell using eco-friendly processing methods

This will be achieved with the development of innovative materials, coatings, processing routes, electrode architectures and cell designs to reduce platinum group metals and other CRMs loading in electrolysers and fuel cells. Novel materials or components will exhibit similar or improved performance and durability compared to state-of-the-art considering SRIA targets. The project also addresses the replacement and/or reduction of non-sustainable or environmentally unacceptable materials, such as organic binders and solvents, as well as the improved management of utilities in manufacturing (power, water) to reduce overall environmental footprint.

O3: Increasing yield of ionomer and CRMs recovered from used cells and membrane electrode assemblies and from scraps and wastes by recycling

This will be achieved with the development of breakthrough high-efficiency solutions for disassembly, recovery, and recycling of critical materials and components in end of life (EoL) cells/stacks and in production wastes, with specific focus on recycling of perfluoro sulfonic acid ionomers for reuse, iridium, Co, Ni and REEs.

O4: Contributing to the development of EU harmonised protocols

This will be achieved with the development of relevant in-situ and operando characterisation and test methods for analysing and quantifying the impacts of new materials and process solutions on

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materials/components/cells characteristics (chemical, mechanical, electrochemical, etc.). Alignment will be made with existing methodologies developed by standardization bodies (e.g. JRC).

O5: Validating new solutions in terms of gain in performance and durability at single cell level

The novel CRM-lean or CRM-free materials and the recycled materials will be validated for their performance and durability in single cells using harmonized protocols, with direct comparison with the performance/durability of cells with current, state-of-the-art materials under the same conditions.

O6: Demonstrating the sustainability of at least three innovative solutions for each technology

This will be achieved based on Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) combined with techno-economic assessment of current and novel technologies (including material supply, manufacturing, operation and recycling processes) driven by an eco-design approach enabling a screening sustainability diagnosis and a more sophisticated multi-objective optimization of the outcomes of LCA and techno-economic analyses. The results of this work will be used for guiding further prioritisation and development in specific dedicated RIAs of the Clean Hydrogen JU.

O7: Maximize impacts, uptake and acceptance of SUSTAINCELL results by developing dissemination, communication and exploitation strategies towards academia, industries, policy makers, NGOs, and public

This will be achieved by engaging with various stakeholders and sharing openly the learnings and challenges of the project to promote knowledge exchange and cross-fertilization of ideas, and to highlight the benefits and impacts of SUSTAINCELL solutions. Extensive focus will be given on dissemination of scientific results and rapid uptake of developments by technology developers/end-users partly facilitated through an advisory board with members from industry, academia and standardization bodies.

O8: Establishing a suitable toolbox for efficient risk management and knowledge sharing between partners

This will be achieved by implementing knowledge management tools and sound quality assurance guidelines piloted by dynamic management teams (Executive board) supported with the appointment of a dissemination manager and an innovation manager.

Table 1: Sets of key performance indicators (KPI) of SUSTAINCELL project.

Key performance indicators	References
CRMs as catalysts in AEL, AEMEL, PEMEL, PEMFC	SRIA targets for 2030: AEL 0.0 mg/W, AEMEL 0.0 mg/W, PEMEL 0.25 mg/W, PEMFC (transport) <0.25 mg/kW; PEMFC (stationary) 0.01 mg/W _{el} non-recoverable CRM
Min. CRMs/PGMs (other than Pt) recycled from scraps and wastes;	SRIA targets for 2030 used for SUSTAINCELL technologies: 50 wt.%
Min. Pt recycled from scraps and wastes;	SRIA targets for 2030: 99 wt.%
Min. ionomer recycled from scraps & wastes	SRIA targets for 2030: 80 wt.%
Current density and degradation rate at cell level for AEL, AEMEL, PEMEL, SOEL	AEL 1A/cm ² @1.8V, 0.1 %/1000h. AEMEL 1.5 A/cm ² @2V, 0.5%/1000 h. PEMEL 3 A/cm ² @1.8V, 0.12%/1000h. SOEL 1.5 A/cm ² @1.2V, 0.5%/1000 h.

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PEMFC electrical efficiency, non-recoverable CRM loading, degradation rate	Extrapolated from SRIA targets for 2030: PEMFC ~56% (% LHV H ₂), 0.01 mg/W _{el} , 0.2%/1000 h
Current density and degradation rate for PCCEL	Initial references based on European project FCH JU GAMER and WINNER led by partner SINTEF: current density > 0.5 A/cm ² @ 1.2V; degradation 1.2%/ 1000 h
Power density, PGM loading, degradation rate for AEM Fuel Cell	Initial references based on CREATE (Horizon 2020) led by partner CNRS; current density > 1A/cm ² ; 0.5%/1000h
Economic indicators: CAPEX	SRIA targets for 2030: @ 100 MW [AEL 400 €/kW, AEMEL 300 €/kW, PEMEL 500 €/kW, SOEL 520 €/kW], @ 500 kWe, PEMFC 900 €/kW]
New project specific KPIs on sustainability and circularity	
New indicators addressing sustainability and circularity to be developed in SUSTAINCELL:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Materials circularity and intensity (e.g. per unit of energy) indicators for CRM Environmental life cycle impact assessment indicators such as impact on climate change, Ecosystem Quality and Human Health and on the dissipation of resources, 	

3 Summary of Innovations anticipated in the project

Innovations to be generated in the project are shown in the figure below.

Figure 2. Targeted innovations in the SUSTAINCELL project.

The development of enhanced recovery and treatment processes for optimising both recovery and reuse of PGMs/ CRMs and ionomers extracted from end-of-life stacks and production processes will furthermore reduce the reliance on import of materials. The novel solutions will be validated at cell level for all technologies using harmonized testing procedures. This ambitious work will be supported by the development and implementation life cycle thinking tools addressing environmental and economic dimensions to drive the research and development work using quantifiable sustainability criteria, as shown below.

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Figure 2. Circular approach of SUSTAINCELL.

4 Additional information

The project started 01/01/2023 and will last 6 years. Total European funding is ca. 10 MEuros.

Contact information - SUSTAINCELL coordinator:

- Dr. Marie-Laure Fontaine
- Research Manager, SINTEF
- Email: marie-laure.fontaine@sintef.no
- Tel: +4793479555